

Kinetics of Polymerization of Acrylamide Initiated by Lead Tetraacetate in Aqueous Acetic Acid

T. BALAKRISHNAN and E. K. KASILINGAM

Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Madras, A. C. College Campus, Madras-600 025

THE oxidation of various organic substrates using lead tetraacetate has been reported¹⁻⁴. Lead tetraacetate has been used as an initiator for the polymerization of methyl methacrylate⁵ in benzene at 60°. The initiating radical was presumed to be the methyl radical resulting from homolysis of the Pb-O bond of lead tetraacetate. Polymerization of methyl methacrylate with lead tetraacetate using a mixed solvent of benzene and acetic acid was carried out⁶. It is surprising that apart from the above two reports, lead tetraacetate has not been widely used for the polymerization of vinyl monomers. Our object is to study the kinetics of polymerization of vinyl monomers and to compare their absolute reactivities using lead tetraacetate.

Experimental

Acrylamide was recrystallized from chloroform. Lead tetraacetate was prepared by a known method from red lead powder⁷. It crystallized from hot glacial acetic acid, containing a small amount of acetic anhydride, in colourless monoclinic crystals, which are best stored moist with a trace of acetic acid. Dry crystals rapidly turned brown on exposure to moist air.

The polymerization was carried out in a glass vessel (80 ml capacity) provided with an inlet and outlet for nitrogen. A constant ionic strength was maintained by the addition of sodium nitrate. The solution was kept acidic by addition of nitric acid. The polymerization reaction was carried out in aqueous acetic acid (50% v/v). The rate of disappearance of monomer was followed by bromometry and that of the initiator by iodometry. The kinetic chain length was determined from the viscosity measurements, using the equation $[\eta] = 6.8 \times 10^{-4} (\bar{M}_v)^{0.66}$ in water at 30°.

Results and Discussion

Polymerization of acrylamide takes place at measurable rates in the temperature range 40–60°. Experiments were carried out to find the attainment of steady state. The steady state is reached after about 10 min. The rate of polymerization, R_p , increased with the monomer concentration and a plot of R_p vs $[M]^2$ indicates that the order with respect to the monomer is 2 (Fig. 1A). When the concentration of the initiator, lead tetraacetate (LTA), is raised from 0.012 to 0.025 mol l⁻¹ R_p increases linearly. A plot of R_p vs [LTA] is linear and passes through the origin, suggesting

the order to be unity. It was also observed that the rate of polymerization is the maximum at an acid concentration of 2 mol l⁻¹. The following

Fig. 1. Rate plots for the system acrylamide/lead tetraacetate (LTA).

- A: R_p vs $[M]^2$. $[H^+] = 2 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $\mu = 2.1 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $T = 60^\circ$; $[LTA] = 0.01688 \text{ mmol l}^{-1}$.
 B: R_p vs $[LTA]$. $[H^+] = 2 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $\mu = 2.1 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $[M] = 0.496 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $T = 60^\circ$.
 C: $\bar{X}_n \times 10^{-3}$ vs $[M]$. $[H^+] = 2 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $\mu = 2.1 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$; $T = 60^\circ$.

kinetic scheme is proposed to explain the experimental observation:

Dedicated with fondness to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee in celebration of his 90th birthday.

The termination of polymerization may take place by abstraction of a proton from the acetic acid. Assuming the steady state conditions, the following expression for the rate of polymerization for the above mechanism is derived :

$$R_p = \frac{2k_a k_i k_p [M]^2 [LTA]}{k_t [AcOH]} \quad \dots (1)$$

Since the experiments are conducted in 50% v/v aqueous acetic acid the concentration of acetic acid is very much higher than that of both the monomer and the lead tetraacetate, the rate expression may be written as :

$$R_p = \frac{2k_a k_i k_p [M]^2 [LTA]}{k_t} \quad \dots (2)$$

It is interesting to note that at concentrations of upto 50 vol % acetic acid R_p remains constant and >60 vol %, the rate of polymerization decreases as expected from eqn. (1). The mechanism of polymerization is confirmed by determining the kinetic chain length. If the above mechanism is operative, the expression for degree of polymerization may be derived as

$$\bar{X}_n = \frac{k_p [M]}{k_t [AcOH]}$$

A plot of \bar{X}_n vs $[M]$ is linear indicating that the termination is by acetic acid. A similar study is in

progress with other monomers like acrylic acid, methacrylic acid, α -bromoacrylic acid, methacrylamide and α -chloroacrylic acid.

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